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2 **Removal of NO at low concentrations from polluted air in semi-closed**
3 **environments by activated biochars from renewables feedstocks**

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16 **Removal of NO at low concentrations from polluted air in semi-closed**
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26 **Abstract**

27 Efficient measures are urgently required in large cities for nitric oxide (NO) elimination
28 from air in urban semi-closed environments (parking lots and tunnels), characterized by
29 low NO concentrations (<10 ppmv) and temperatures. One of the most promising
30 abatement alternatives is the NO oxidation to NO₂, which can be further easily captured
31 in an alkali solution or over a porous solid. However, most of the research devoted to this
32 topic is focused on the elimination of NO from fuel exhaust gases, with high NO
33 concentrations (400–2000 ppmv). In this work, sustainable and low-cost activated
34 biochars of different origin and having very different ash contents were employed in NO
35 removal at very low concentrations. Thus, low ash content forestry (oak woodchips,
36 OAK) and high ash content from agriculture (oilseed rape straw, OSR) biochars were
37 subjected to physical activation with CO₂ at 900 °C (OAK550-A900CO₂ and OSR700-
38 A900CO₂, respectively). The NO removal performance tests of such activated carbons
39 were carried out at different experimental conditions: i.e., temperature, relative humidity
40 (0–50 vol% RH), NO-containing gas (N₂ or air), amount of activated carbon, and NO
41 concentration, to assess how the activated biochar properties influence their NO removal
42 capacity. The sample OSR700-A900CO₂ contained a higher population of oxygen surface
43 functionalities, which might play an important role in the NO removal efficiency in dry
44 conditions since they could assist NO oxidation on carbon active sites when used above
45 room temperature (50–75 °C). However, at room temperature (25 °C), the presence of
46 narrow micropore size distribution at 6 Å became a more relevant property, since it

47 facilitates an intimate contact between NO and O₂. Accordingly, the activated biochar
48 from OAK was much more efficient, achieving complete removal of NO from air flow
49 (dry or with 50 vol% RH) at 25 °C during 400 min of testing, making it an ideal candidate
50 as biofilter for purifying air streams of semi-closed spaces contaminated with low
51 concentrations of NO.

52 **Keywords:** polluted air, activated carbon, carbonaceous catalysts, low concentration NO,
53 NO oxidation, NO_x elimination

54 **1. Introduction**

55 Anthropogenic nitrogen oxides (NO_x) are considered important atmospheric pollutants
56 as they are the main precursors of negative environmental impacts, such as acid rain and
57 photochemical smog, causing severe harmful effects on human health. These issues are
58 particularly severe in large cities as a consequence of the increasing road transport due to
59 the huge growth of population and standard of living in urban areas (Shaw and Van Heyst,
60 2022; Wang et al., 2015). Therefore, more stringent restrictions have been imposed by
61 most of the authorities in developed countries. For instance, the European Ambient Air
62 Quality Directive (EU, 2008) established more restrictive NO_x concentrations thresholds,
63 setting hourly and yearly limit values of 200 and 40 µg/m³, respectively (Derwent and
64 Hjellbrekke, 2019). However, these air quality standards are particularly difficult to
65 achieve in those semi-closed environments (road tunnels and parking lots), where there
66 is generally low ventilation efficiency and automobile exhaust emissions are
67 concentrated, causing the risk of health problems (Demir, 2015). In particular, in such
68 located spaces, the concentration of NO_x usually is very low, reaching values up to 10
69 ppmv, containing approximately 90% nitric oxide (NO) (Pan et al., 2017). This is a much
70 lower concentration than the typical considered in most studies regarding the treatment
71 of NO_x-contaminated gases. This fact, along with the ambient air conditions in such
72 spaces (low temperature and variable relative humidity) makes particularly challenging
73 any de-NO_x in-situ application.

74 Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) is the most widely used technology for the
75 abatement of NO emissions in flue gas effluents produced by stationary sources (Feng et
76 al., 2022; Gui et al., 2022). In the case of mobile sources, SCR is also a mature process
77 for diesel vehicles; whereas, for gasoline engines, NO emissions can be effectively
78 controlled with three-way catalysts (TWCs). However, these systems are only effective

79 for high NO concentrations, operating at high temperatures (300–400 °C), oxygen
80 concentrations close to stoichiometric combustion, and require the utilization of
81 expensive metal-based catalysts (Brandenberger et al., 2008). Accordingly, these
82 technologies are not appropriate for NO_x removal in semi-closed spaces, mainly
83 characterized by a low NO_x concentration under ambient conditions (relatively low
84 temperatures and high oxygen concentration).

85 As an alternative, NO catalytic oxidation is considered a highly-effective option for NO
86 removal at low temperatures (<100 °C). At high concentrations, NO is very reactive with
87 oxygen, yielding NO₂, which can be subsequently captured in an aqueous solution or
88 easily adsorbed on porous solids (Hong et al., 2017; Shen et al., 2016). However, at values
89 lower than 1000 ppmv, NO is very stable, hindering its oxidative removal in air and
90 requiring the use of highly active catalysts (Mochida et al., 1997, 1994). Carbonaceous
91 solids (activated carbons, CNFs, CNTs, graphene oxides, xerogels, etc.) provide
92 numerous benefits as low-temperature NO oxidation catalysts, such as their excellent
93 catalytic performance at room temperature and low energy requirements (Anthonysamy
94 et al., 2022; Deng et al., 2020; Silas et al., 2019).

95 Lignocellulosic precursors, such as pyrolysis biochars, have been widely used as low-cost
96 and renewable raw materials to prepare active carbons for a wide range of applications as
97 adsorbents and catalysts (Azargohar and Dalai, 2006; Nor et al., 2013). Both physical
98 (CO₂ and steam) and chemical processes (KOH, K₂CO₃, HNO₃, etc) can be applied to
99 provide biochars with different textural and chemical properties. The activation
100 conditions (temperature, time, and gasifying or chemical reagents employed), as well as
101 the nature of the raw biomass used as feedstock, are the main factors influencing the final
102 properties of the activated biochars (Gwenzi et al., 2021; Jeguirim et al., 2018; Kalinke
103 et al., 2017; Qu et al., 2021; Siipola et al., 2018).

104 Nonetheless, despite the huge potential presented by those carbon materials, the reaction
105 mechanism and the carbon characteristics that promote the oxidation process are not
106 completely elucidated (Deng et al., 2020; Qiu et al., 2009; Valenciano et al., 2015). Thus,
107 Zhang et al. investigated NO oxidation over a variety of active carbons with different
108 textural properties concluding that NO₂ formation is favoured by the presence of narrow
109 micropores (~ 6–7 Å), which provide very close contact between NO and O₂, not being
110 influenced by the overall surface area neither by the chemical properties (Zhang et al.,
111 2008). The presence of oxygenated and nitrogen surface groups are also relevant features
112 for the NO oxidation process since they affect the kinetics of NO/NO₂ adsorption-

113 desorption, increasing the rate of NO oxidation (Adapa et al., 2006; Atkinson et al., 2013).
114 In this regard, recently, Wang et al. described that the presence of small traces of
115 potassium in coal-derived carbons prepared by hydrothermal activation with K_2CO_3
116 might promote the formation of oxygenated functional groups (C–O) when these were
117 subjected to a simulated flue gas containing oxygen, resulting in an improved removal of
118 low concentration NO at 50 °C (Wang et al., 2022). However, it is important to highlight
119 that most of the works devoted to this topic investigated the NO_x removal capacity of
120 carbonaceous solids, with different physicochemical properties, from gaseous streams at
121 high NO_x concentrations (200–2000 ppmv) and relatively low temperatures (30-50 °C).
122 Conversely, there are hardly any works in the scientific literature focused on the particular
123 application of carbonaceous solids in the NO_x abatement at low concentrations (<10 ppm)
124 (G. Diaz-Maroto et al., 2023; Ghouma et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2011) as are those usually
125 found in semi-closed spaces of urban areas. This issue is considered a great challenge
126 because of the scarce reactivity of NO when it is found at very low concentrations and
127 low temperatures. Ghouma et al. (Ghouma et al., 2017) evaluated the performance of
128 agro-industrial derived carbons on the NO₂ removal at a concentration of 5 ppmv and 23
129 °C, but not on the NO elimination. However, unlike NO, NO₂ shows a high affinity to be
130 adsorbed on the surface of porous solids. On the other hand, Wang et al. prepared Porous
131 Carbon Nanofibers (PCNFs) derived from synthetic Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fibres,
132 which were able to remove up to 60 or 100 % of NO, depending on the NO inlet
133 concentration (2 and 20 ppm, respectively) at 30 °C (Wang et al., 2011). Alternatively,
134 there are also a very limited number of works, in which metal oxides (e.g MnO_x, Mg-
135 doped MnO_x or Fe/Mn binary oxides) have been tested under experimental conditions
136 (10 ppm NO and room temperature), similar to those of semi-closed urban spaces, giving
137 100% NO removal efficiency (Pan et al., 2017; Shu et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2015).
138 Nevertheless, in a recent work, we investigated the effect of physical activation conditions
139 (temperature, activating agent) on the NO removal efficiency using a pyrolysis biochar
140 as carbon precursor, with which we achieved the total NO removal (5 ppmv) from a gas
141 flow (with > 5 vol% O₂) (G. Diaz-Maroto et al., 2023).
142 In this context, the main novelty and motivation of this work are to investigate the
143 behaviour on the NO removal at low concentrations and temperatures using low-cost and
144 renewable activated carbons obtained from the activation of biochars, obtained as by-
145 product in two kinds of pyrolysis reactors operating under different experimental
146 conditions to produce bio-oil (as main product) for biofuels or biochemical applications.

147 Two residues with very different origin and ash content, oak (OAK550) and oilseed rape
148 straw (OSR700), were used as feedstocks. The biochars were physically activated with
149 CO₂ and evaluated as NO retention filters simulating the air conditions found in semi-
150 closed and low-ventilated urban spaces (e.g., road tunnels or parking lots), having low
151 NO concentration (2.5–7.5 ppmv) and low-moderate temperatures (25–75 °C). Special
152 attention has been paid to the role of textural properties and surface chemistry in NO
153 removal.

154 **2. Materials and Methods**

155 **2.1. Materials**

156 In this study, two biomass residues with diverse origin (forest and agricultural), ash
157 content and pyrolysed in two kinds of reactors operated under different experimental
158 conditions, were selected as carbonaceous precursors to produce activated carbons and
159 compare their NO removal capacity from polluted gaseous streams. On the one hand, oak
160 woodchips, in form of small particles 1–2 mm of diameter, was pyrolysed at 550 °C, with
161 a heating rate of 10 °C/min and a N₂ total flow rate of 4 L/min with a residence time of
162 60 min in a fixed-bed reactor, producing a biochar yield of 17 wt.%, named OAK550. On
163 the other hand, oilseed rape straw (OSR), in form of pellets with an average size of 10
164 mm length and 5 mm diameter, was pyrolysed at 700 °C, with a heating rate of 100 °C/min
165 and a biomass residence of time of 12 min in a rotatory kiln reactor, giving rise to a
166 biochar yield of 23 wt.%, named OSR700 (Mašek et al., 2018).

167 **2.2. Biochar activation**

168 *Physical activation: CO₂*

169 Both OAK550 and OSR700 biochars were physically activated with CO₂ using a lab-
170 scale setup, whose schematic diagram is represented in Figure S1. A detailed description
171 of the setup and the activation experimental procedure can be found in the Supplementary
172 Material. The resulting activated carbons were denoted as OAK550-A900CO₂ and
173 OSR700-A900CO₂, respectively.

174 The degree of activation or *burn-off* level was calculated according to Equation 1.

$$175 \quad \text{Burn-off (wt. \%)} = \frac{W_{0,\text{daf}} - W_{f,\text{daf}}}{W_{0,\text{daf}}} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

176 Where $W_{0,daf}$ and $W_{f,daf}$ refer to the initial and final sample weight (in dry and ash free
177 basis), respectively, during the isothermal stage at 900 °C under CO₂ flow.

178 **2.3. Physico-chemical characterisation of samples**

179 Proximate analysis (moisture, volatile matter, and ash contents) of raw biochars and
180 activated carbons were determined according to European standards. Ultimate analysis
181 (elemental composition) of biochars and activated samples was determined in a Thermo
182 Scientific FLASH 2000 CHNS/O micro-elemental analyser, where C, H, N and S
183 concentrations were obtained, while O concentration was calculated by difference. The
184 ash fraction obtained from the calcination of the carbonaceous samples was analysed by
185 Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) with a Perkin
186 Elmer Optima 3300 DV instrument. Textural properties of the activated carbons were
187 measured by N₂ and CO₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K and 273 K,
188 respectively, in a Micromeritics 3Flex analyser equipped with a high-vacuum system and
189 three 0.1 Torr pressure transducers. Fourier transform infrared spectra (FT-IR) were
190 measured in a Thermo Fisher Scientific Nicolet 6700 equipped with a ceramic source,
191 KBr beam splitter and a DTGS detector. The existence of oxygenated surface groups in
192 activated biochars was analysed by Temperature Programmed Desorption coupled to
193 Mass Spectroscopy (TPD-MS) by means of monitoring the evolved CO, CO₂ and H₂O
194 during heating treatment. All of the above techniques for the physico-chemical
195 characterisation of the activated biochars and the corresponding experimental procedures
196 have been described in the Supplementary Material.

197 **NO removal tests from polluted air streams**

198 The NO removal tests were carried out in a lab-scale filter, whose schematic diagram is
199 depicted in Figure 1. This setup consisted of a glass updraft fixed-bed column (500 mm
200 length, 16 mm internal diameter) with a porous plate, in which the activated carbon was
201 placed. This area was covered with a heating tape to control the temperature of the
202 removal tests. The gas inlet stream was generated in a NO_x calibrator (Ecotech Serinus
203 3000) containing three gases: air (air zero generator), N₂ (99.999 vol.%), and 50 ppmv
204 NO (balance N₂). The NO_x calibrator set the inlet concentration of NO and O₂ in the gas
205 stream, whose total flow was 1000 mL/min. The gas outlet concentrations were
206 continuously measured with the NO_x (NO and NO₂, with a detection limit of 1 ppb)
207 analyser Ecotech Serinus 40. However, in the course of the experiments here performed,

208 the NO₂ concentration at the outlet of the filter remained almost invariable at negligible
 209 values. Thus, the results of the tests were represented on NO breakthrough curves,
 210 plotting C/C₀ versus time, where C and C₀ are the NO instant outlet and the inlet
 211 concentrations (ppmv), respectively.

212
 213 **Figure 1.** Schematic diagram of the lab-scale filter to remove NO_x (NO and NO₂) from
 214 contaminated gaseous streams

215 In this study, key process conditions, such as operating temperature (25–75 °C), the
 216 presence of relative humidity (0 and 50 vol% RH) in the air stream, NO concentration
 217 ($[NO]_{in} = 2.5–7.5$ ppmv), gas stream nature (air or nitrogen) and carbon load (1.5 and 3
 218 g) were evaluated over the NO removal performance of the prepared materials for 400
 219 min.

220 The total NO elimination capacity was calculated by Equation 2.

$$221 \quad NO_{elimination} (\%) = \frac{NO_{in}(mg) - NO_{out}(mg)}{NO_{in}(mg)} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

222 Where, NO_{in} and NO_{out} represent the total amount of NO (in mg) fed and remaining in the
 223 exhaust gas, respectively; and NO_i (i.e. NO_{in} and NO_{out}) was calculated by Equation 3.

$$224 \quad NO_i (mg) = \frac{Q_{air\ in} (mL/min) \cdot [NO]_{in} (ppmv) \cdot 1 \text{ atm}}{0.082 \left(\frac{atm \cdot mL}{mmol \cdot K} \right) \cdot 298K} \cdot 30 \left(\frac{mgNO}{mmolNO} \right) \cdot time (min) \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

225 Where: $Q_{air\ in} = 1000$ mL/min; $[NO]_{in} = 2.5 – 7.5$ ppmv and $time = 400$ min

226 3. Results and discussion

227 3.1. Physico-chemical characterization of carbonaceous materials

228 Two pyrolysis biochars obtained from different biomass residues of forest (oak
 229 woodchips, OAK550) and agricultural origin (oilseed rape straw, OSR700) with very
 230 different ash content were selected as raw materials for the preparation of activated
 231 carbons via physical activation with CO₂ at 900 °C. First, both raw biochars and the
 232 corresponding activated carbons were characterized to elucidate how the properties and
 233 origin of the raw biochar can affect the physicochemical features of the final active
 234 carbon.

235 Table 1 presents the proximate and ultimate analyses of both raw biochars (OSR700 and
 236 OAK550) and the resulting carbons after physical activation with CO₂ at 900 °C. The
 237 *burn-off* or activation degree determined according to Equation 1 is also included.

238 As can be observed, both raw biochars contain a similar amount of volatile components
 239 (ca. 13.7–14 wt.%, respectively). However, the oilseed rape straw biochar (OSR700)
 240 presents a much higher ash content than that determined from the forestry residue
 241 (OAK550), that is 22.4 vs 1.5 wt.%, respectively, which is in good agreement with the
 242 literature (Fermoso et al., 2017). Consequently, the fixed carbon percentage is
 243 significantly higher in this last sample, reaching a value of 84.5 wt.%. According to the
 244 CHNS/O elemental analysis, OAK550 biochar presents significantly lower oxygen
 245 content than OSR700 (6.5 vs 10.4 wt.%), which denotes a lower amount of oxygenated
 246 surface functional groups.

247 **Table 1.** Proximate and ultimate analysis of both raw biochars and derived activated
 248 carbons.

Sample	<i>Burn-off</i> (wt.%)	Proximate Analysis, db (wt.%)			Ultimate Analysis, daf (wt.%)				
		Volatile Matter	Ash	Fixed Carbon	C	H	N	S	O
OAK550	-	14.0	1.5	84.5	91.2	2.3	0.1	0.0	6.5
OAK550-A900CO ₂	26.9	0.0	2.1	97.9	96.1	0.5	0.2	0.0	3.2
OSR700	-	13.7	22.4	63.9	87.0	1.5	1.1	0.0	10.4
OSR700-A900CO ₂	30.1	0.0	32.8	67.2	91.8	0.9	1.3	0.0	6.0

249 db: dry basis; daf: dry and ash-free basis

250 The volatile matter was fully removed in both activated carbons, regardless of their origin.
 251 Such elimination mainly occurred during the heating-up period under nitrogen flow,
 252 before the CO₂ activation at 900 °C stage. Then, once the activation temperature was

253 reached, CO₂ reacts with the carbon surface, opening the porous structure of the biochar
 254 by extracting part of the carbon atoms. But the surface chemistry of the remaining carbon
 255 can be also modified since oxygenated species can be partially released due to the high
 256 activation temperature (900 °C) applied. Thus, the elemental analysis, on dry and ash-free
 257 basis, shows a C enrichment to the detriment of H and O contents (Chen et al., 2017;
 258 Zhang et al., 2014). Therefore, those activated carbons are deeply carbonized materials,
 259 being constituted mostly by aromatic structures (Hwang et al., 2017; Janu et al., 2021;
 260 Jouiad et al., 2015). After the activation process, the ash content of both samples
 261 augments proportionally to those values of the raw biochars (as they remain in the solid),
 262 according to their burn-off degree. In this regard, for OSR700-A900CO₂, this share
 263 increases significantly, from 22.4 up to 32.8 wt.%, while in the case of OAK550-
 264 A900CO₂, this value varies from 1.5 to 2.1 wt.%. The burn-off percentage estimated for
 265 the OSR700-A900CO₂ is somewhat higher than that determined for the OAK550-
 266 activated biochar. This difference could denote a certain catalytic effect of the mineral
 267 fraction contained in this sample, particularly rich in K (see Table 2), which may favor
 268 CO₂ gasification reactions by reducing the activation energy (E_a) during the gasification
 269 process (Hu et al., 2019).

270 **Table 2.** ICP-OES analysis of activated carbons prepared from CO₂ activation of
 271 OAK550 and OSR700 biochars.

Element, db (wt.%)	Al	Ca	Fe	K	Mg	Na	P	Others (<0.1 wt.%)	Ash
OAK550- A900CO ₂	0.03	1.65	0.01	0.17	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.08	2.1
OSR700- A900CO ₂	0.15	10.3	0.53	18.08	1.10	0.59	1.83	0.16	32.8

272 db: dry basis

273 N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K for both activated carbons are depicted in
 274 Figure 2. They exhibit combined features of type I (b) and IV, according to the IUPAC
 275 classification. Thus, a strong N₂ uptake occurs at relative pressures lower than 0.1, which
 276 denotes the predominance of a well-developed microporosity. The wide “knee” curvature
 277 of the isotherm at these relative pressures indicates that this microporosity is relatively
 278 heterogeneous in size (Thommes et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2012). In addition, the
 279 progressive adsorption produced at intermediate P/P₀ values denotes the formation of a

280 broad mesoporosity during the activation process. Both isotherms show a relatively
281 narrow H4 hysteresis loop in the range of low-medium pressures, which is usually
282 assigned to the presence of micropores with slit geometry.

283

284 **Figure 2.** N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K for activated carbons prepared from
285 CO₂ activation of OAK550 and OSR700 biochars.

286 The substantial difference observed in the N₂ volume adsorbed indicates that OAK550-
287 A900CO₂ presents higher adsorption capacity, especially in the micropore range, than the
288 activated carbon derived from OSR700. This variation is confirmed by the CO₂
289 physisorption analyses depicted in Figure S2, which were performed to complement the
290 analysis of the textural properties in the narrow micropore zone.

291 The values of the textural properties determined for these samples (Table 3) follow a
292 similar trend. Thus, the S_{BET} (m²/g_{db}) corresponding to the OAK activated biochar is
293 higher than that of OSR700-A900CO₂. This increase is attributed to the major
294 contribution of the microporous system, but also the external porosity (associated with
295 both meso- and macropores) generated during the CO₂ activation process. These results
296 can be assigned to the higher proportion of inorganic matter in OSR-derived biochar,
297 which does not show any porous structure. In fact, if the specific surface areas were
298 estimated referred to the mass of organic matter (i.e. per gram in dry and ash free basis),
299 the OSR700-A900CO₂ would reach a value of 788 m²/g_{daf}, being somewhat higher than
300 that estimated for the OAK550-activated biochar, which will show a value of 735 m²/g_{daf}.

301

302 **Table 3.** Textural properties of the activated carbons prepared from CO₂ activation of
303 OAK550 and OSR700 biochars (determined from N₂ isotherms).

Sample	S _{BET} (m ² /g _{db})	S _{MIC} (m ² /g _{db})	S _{EXT} (m ² /g _{db})	V _{MIC} (cm ³ /g _{db})	V _{Total} (cm ³ /g _{db})
OAK550-A900CO ₂	723	456	267	0.18	0.397
OSR700-A900CO ₂	530	346	184	0.14	0.307

304 S_{BET}: BET surface area; S_{MIC} (micropore surface area), S_{EXT} (external surface area) and V_{MIC} (micropore
305 volume) calculated using the t-plot method; V_{Total}: total pore volume at P/P₀ ≈ 0.97.

306 Through the combination of both CO₂ and N₂ isotherms, the pore size distribution (PSD)
307 of the two activated carbons was determined by applying the model 2D-NLDFT and
308 considering a slit pore geometry (Figure 3). For clarity, the CO₂ isotherm is used to define
309 the ultra-small microporosity zone (pore size < 10 Å) while the N₂ isotherm allows the
310 estimation of the pore size distribution in the large-microporous and mesoporous range
311 (pore size > 10 Å) (Jagiello et al., 2019). As can be observed, both samples exhibit a wide
312 pore size distribution typical of activated carbons obtained by physical activation methods
313 (Lozano-Castelló et al., 2004). OAK550 activated carbon presents a bimodal pore size
314 distribution comprising a microporosity with an average diameter of 6 Å, and a secondary
315 broad mesoporosity centred at around 37 Å. The presence of micropores around ~ 6–7 Å
316 could be a positive feature, as this value is considered to be optimal for NO removal
317 (Zhang et al., 2008; Zhu et al., 2022).

318 In contrast, in the case of OSR700-A900CO₂, the PSD reveals the existence of trimodal
319 porous structure, showing broad microporosity with a significant contribution of
320 micropores with sizes around 6 and 10 Å, together with a broad mesoporosity centred at
321 36 Å. It should be noticed that the cumulative pore volume of the micropores with an
322 average diameter of 6 Å is much higher in OAK550-A900CO₂ than that exhibited by
323 OSR700-A900CO₂, showing values of 0.5 and 0.26 cm³/g, respectively. This difference
324 is still maintained even if it was estimated regarding the carbonaceous matter content (0.5
325 cm³/g vs 0.39 cm³/g) which would be indicative that OAK activated carbon has a higher
326 proportion of micropores of this size.

327

328

329 **Figure 3.** 2D-NLDFT pore size distributions of the activated carbons derived from
 330 OAK550 (A) and OSR700 (B) biochars.

331 Analyses of the chemical groups on the surface of activated carbons were attempted by
 332 FT-IR and TPD-MS techniques. Figure 4 shows the FT-IR spectra for the raw biochars
 333 (A, B) and activated carbons (C, D), respectively. A higher amount of surface
 334 functionalities in OSR700 than in OAK550 is detected according to the larger intensity
 335 of the different registered bands. Of particular larger intensities are the bands appearing
 336 at wavenumbers of 750–900 cm⁻¹ and 1030 cm⁻¹, assigned to the stretching of the aryl C–
 337 H and C–O bonds and the C–O and C–O–C, respectively. The O–H band at 3700 cm⁻¹ is
 338 also more intense. Finally, there are also two intense peaks at 1600 cm⁻¹ and 1200 cm⁻¹
 339 corresponding to the stretching vibration of the carbonyl group (C=O) and from the C–O
 340 stretching vibration of anhydride and ether groups, respectively.

341

342 **Figure 4.** FT-IR spectra of raw biochars (A, B) and derived activated carbons (C, D).

343 The activation with CO₂ of OAK-derived biochar caused a strong reduction of the
 344 absorption bands (Figure 4D) associated with the presence of oxygenated functional
 345 groups (Wang et al., 2022). The elimination of these surface functionalities is relatively
 346 predictable for those processes involving high operating temperatures, like physical
 347 activation with CO₂ at 900 °C. Accordingly, the chemical groups present on the carbon
 348 surface are partially removed due to bonding destruction and self-cracking reactions
 349 (Armynah et al., 2019; Barroso-Bogeat et al., 2019; Lu et al., 2017). However, after the
 350 activation process, OSR700-A900CO₂ preserves almost all the oxygenated functional
 351 groups on the surface according to the corresponding FT-IR spectrum, which agrees with
 352 its higher oxygen content in the elemental analysis (see Table 1). This finding could be
 353 related to the presence of a significant amount of K in the mineral fraction of the OSR700
 354 biochar. As reported elsewhere, K may act as catalyst promoting the formation of surface
 355 oxygenated groups, in particular, those with carbonyl and hydroxyl functionalities (J.
 356 Zhao et al., 2016). Therefore, the stronger elimination of oxygenated groups detected in

357 low ash biochars would be counteracted in case there is a significant amount of potassium
358 in the carbon matrix.

359 To corroborate this effect, the activated biochars were subjected to TPD-MS analyses.
360 This technique allows to determine what kind of oxygenated functional groups are present
361 on the carbon surface following the evolution of the release of CO, CO₂ and/or H₂O with
362 the temperature (Bedia et al., 2018; Figueiredo and Pereira, 2010; Ishii and Kyotani,
363 2016). The spectra so obtained are displayed in Figure 5. Thus, regarding the H₂O profile,
364 OSR700 derived carbon presents an intense broad band (150–400 °C) with three
365 maximums centred at 200, 275 and 325 °C, the latter being assigned to the chemisorbed
366 water that would be evolved due to dehydration of neighbour hydroxyl groups, leading to
367 the formation of the carboxylic anhydride, which decomposes to CO and CO₂ at higher
368 temperatures (350–627 °C) (Ghouma et al., 2015; Otake and Jenkins, 1993; Shafeeyan et
369 al., 2010). Then, in the CO desorption profile, this sample experiences an important
370 increase at higher temperatures, being associated with carboxylic anhydrides (350–600
371 °C), phenol (600–700 °C), and especially to neutral or basic oxygenated functional
372 groups: carbonyl and quinones (700–900 °C) (Shafeeyan et al., 2010; Shen et al., 2012).
373 Finally, regarding CO₂ desorption, this is related to acidic groups, and, in this case, it
374 exhibits a broad desorption band with a maximum peak centred at 250 °C, along with a
375 shoulder at 325 °C, which could be associated with the presence of carboxylic (150–400
376 °C) and lactone (200–600 °C) groups. There is an additional broad band (350–600 °C)
377 that can be assigned to the carboxylic anhydride decomposition with a maximum peak
378 centred at high temperature (600 °C) (Shafeeyan et al., 2010; Shen et al., 2012). These
379 results clearly denote that OSR700-A900CO₂ presents a wide variety of oxygenated
380 groups, being much higher than in the case of the OAK derived biochar. As was above
381 described, K may promote the formation of oxygenated moieties related to C–O bonds,
382 which improves the NO removal performance of carbon materials (Wang et al., 2022; Y.
383 Zhao et al., 2016) It is remarkable that activated biochars present a different relation
384 between carboxylic and anhydride groups. In this respect, OSR700-A900CO₂ contains
385 the same amount of both groups, while OAK550-A900CO₂ presents a lower proportion
386 of carboxylic groups.

387

388

389 **Figure 5.** H₂O (A), CO (B) and CO₂ (C) TPD-MS spectra of activated carbons derived
 390 from OSR700 and OAK550 biochars.

391 **3.2. NO removal activity tests from polluted gaseous streams**

392 After the activated carbons derived from different biochars were physico-chemically
 393 characterised, their performance on the NO elimination at low concentrations was

394 evaluated. For that purpose, different experimental conditions, such as temperature, NO
395 concentration, flue gas diluent (N₂ or air), and activated carbon load, were tested to
396 investigate how they influence the NO removal efficiency and to assess which carbon
397 features are more relevant in the oxidation/elimination process. First, blank tests
398 consisting of passing N₂ or air flows containing NO through the unloaded filter, were
399 carried out to assess if the oxidation of NO to NO₂ could take place in the gas phase under
400 oxidizing atmospheres in absence of activated carbon. In these experiments, no variation
401 was observed in the outlet NO concentration with respect to the initial, as well as
402 negligible NO₂ concentrations, corroborating that the oxidation of NO to NO₂ is
403 insignificant in the gas phase in the absence of solid carbon, which confirms previous
404 results in the literature indicating the need of a solid catalyst to oxidize NO to NO₂ (Shen
405 et al., 2016; Tsukahara et al., 1999).

406 *Effect of temperature on the NO removal capacity from air streams*

407 The effect of the temperature during the adsorption tests on the NO elimination capacity
408 was evaluated under air flow. In this sense, Figure 6 depicts the total NO removal capacity
409 of activated biochars at 25, 50 and 75 °C as a function of the NO concentrations at the
410 reactor inlet. The rise in the temperature enhances the NO removal efficiency of the
411 OSR700-derived carbon by approximately 37%, achieving a complete elimination of NO
412 when the experiment is performed at 50 °C. This significant improvement of the OSR700-
413 A900CO₂ capacity could be derived from the considerable amount of oxygenated surface
414 functionalities, which might be activated by temperature, promoting the NO to NO₂
415 oxidation that would remain easily adsorbed on the material surface. Moreover, in this
416 case, when the temperature is slightly increased, the potassium contained in the mineral
417 fraction could also promote the formation of surface C–O bonds, which increases the NO
418 oxidation rate, leading to better NO removal efficiencies. A similar effect has been
419 previously reported with coal-activated carbons doped with K traces and corroborated by
420 DFT simulation (Wang et al., 2022). Nevertheless, to discard the catalytic activity of the
421 mineral fraction in the NO oxidation process, an additional NO removal test was
422 performed using an ash bed obtained from the combustion of the OSR700 activated
423 carbon. In this experiment, NO removal was null, which confirms that NO oxidation is
424 catalyzed by the surface active sites of the carbonaceous fraction of the biochar.

425

426 **Figure 6.** Effect of the adsorption temperature on the NO removal capacity of activated
 427 carbons derived from OAK and OSR biochars under air flow. Experimental conditions:
 428 $[\text{NO}]_0 = 5$ ppmv; activated carbon bed: 3 g. Overlapped striped columns: 50 vol% HR in
 429 air flow.

430 In contrast, OAK550-A900CO₂ leads to a complete removal of NO at 25 °C, being
 431 significantly higher than that exhibited by OSR700-derived activated biochar. However,
 432 its NO removal capacity decreased to some extent from 100 to 92–93% when the
 433 temperature increased up to 50 °C. This different behavior of both samples indicates that,
 434 at room temperature, NO removal process is favoured by the higher specific surface area
 435 and, especially, the narrower micropore size close to 6 Å of OAK550-A900CO₂. In this
 436 sense, considering that, before the oxidation itself, both NO and O₂ are initially co-
 437 adsorbed in the carbon micropores, these results suggest that, over the OAK activated
 438 biochar, the reactants co-adsorption step is the controlling stage, being unfavored at
 439 temperatures higher than the ambient.

440 Moreover, these carbons were also tested under humid air (50 vol% HR) at 25 °C, whose
 441 results are presented as overlapped striped columns in Figure 6. Here, it can be observed
 442 that OSR-derived material presents a 47.8 % loss of NO removal efficiency. This result
 443 might be linked to the higher proportion of oxygenated surface functional groups (see
 444 Figure 5), due to water molecules associate to form clusters around those oxygen-
 445 containing functional groups, which may hinder pore entrance, (De Ridder et al., 2012;

446 Do et al., 2009; Nakamura et al., 2010) inhibiting partially the NO and O₂ interaction with
447 the carbon surface. Thus, in the case of OAK-derived carbon, which possess very low
448 proportion of oxygenated surface groups, the NO removal performance was hardly altered
449 in presence of moisture, denoting that the more hydrophobic character of the carbon
450 surface prevents the adsorption of water molecules on the active sites.
451 Therefore, it could be affirmed that OAK550-A900CO₂ would be a more convenient
452 material for the removal of low concentrations of NO at room temperature and certain
453 relative humidity, which are the typical conditions in semi-close spaces of urban areas.

454 *Effect of NO concentration of polluted air streams and amount of carbon*

455 The effect of the NO concentration (2.5–7.5 ppmv) in the air stream was also evaluated
456 at 25 °C. Since the OAK550-derived sample achieved a full NO removal in the previous
457 experiments (Figure 7), and in order to appreciate more significant differences between
458 both activated carbons, the amount of sample used in these assays was reduced to half
459 (1.5 g). In this figure, the first observation is that reducing the carbon material to half
460 caused a decrease of 36 and 40 % in the removal capacity of both activated biochars with
461 an NO inlet concentration of 5 ppmv. This means that the reduction of the carbon bed
462 limits the contact time between carbon and reactants (NO and O₂) hindering the complete
463 removal of all the NO passing through. This effect occurs even employing half pollutant
464 concentration (2.5 ppmv), at which none of the materials was able to fully remove the NO
465 fed during the whole experiment. This effect was even more noticeable in the case of the
466 OSR700 activated carbon. These results indicate that the process is more sensitive to the
467 amount of carbon and, accordingly, to the contact time, when the adsorption process is
468 chemically controlled by the interaction of oxygenated surface groups, as occurs in the
469 OSR700-derived activated carbon. In this regard, if the NO removed percentages were
470 estimated on an ash-free basis, taking into account just the amount of carbon in the
471 sample, in all cases, the elimination capacity of OAK550-A900CO₂ was significantly
472 higher.

473

474 **Figure 7.** NO removal capacity of activated carbons as a function of the NO concentration
 475 in the air stream. Experimental conditions: Temperature: 25 °C; carbon bed: 1.5 g.

476 ***Breakthrough curves and total NO removal capacity of activated carbons***

477 Finally, the NO breakthrough curves at room temperature (25 °C) in air and nitrogen flue
 478 gas are shown in Figure 8. Both activated carbons, regardless of their origin, show a much
 479 better NO removal capacity in air than in N₂ flow, which demonstrates the key role of the
 480 presence of oxygen in the gas phase to assist the oxidation of NO to NO₂ on active sites
 481 of carbon materials as explained in a previous work (G. Diaz-Maroto et al., 2023).
 482 Important differences are observed between the two activated carbons in terms of NO
 483 removal along the time. In this regard, while OAK550-A900CO₂ was able to entirely
 484 remove the NO (99.9%) from the air flow during the 400 min of the test, the OSR700
 485 activated carbon did not totally eliminate the NO from the start of the experiment, with
 486 C/C₀ values continuously increasing with time up to final values of 0.51, which was
 487 reflected in its quite inferior total removal capacity of 62.7%. This result could be related,
 488 as above discussed, to the higher S_{BET} area and, in particular, the narrower micropore size
 489 distribution of OAK550-A900CO₂. As it is previously mentioned, homogeneous
 490 micropores with sizes close to ~6–7 Å allow intimate contact between NO and O₂, which
 491 had molecular sizes of 0.317 nm and 0.346 nm, respectively, acting as nanoreactors for
 492 the NO oxidation process (Zhu et al., 2022).

493

494 **Figure 8.** Breakthrough curves of NO removal of activated carbons in air and N₂ flue
 495 gases. Experimental conditions: [NO]₀=5 ppmv; Temperature: 25 °C; carbon bed: 3 g.

496 The NO removal capacity gets much worse in absence of molecular oxygen in the gas
 497 stream, and in particular, in the case of OAK550-derived carbon. Thus, the activated
 498 carbons exhibit a very low NO removal efficiency in nitrogen flow, achieving C/C₀ values
 499 in the range of 0.6–0.9 at a time of 120 min. This fact suggests that, in the absence of
 500 oxygen, the oxygenated surface functional groups may assist the NO oxidation over
 501 carbons (Deng et al., 2020). Thus, OSR700-A900CO₂ shows better NO removal capacity
 502 in N₂ than in the other carbon. From these results, it can be envisaged that the NO removal
 503 process, in presence of oxygen, is controlled by the textural properties of the
 504 carbonaceous solid while, under nitrogen flow, is dominated by the chemical surface
 505 properties of the activated carbon, such as the oxygen functional groups.

506 **Conclusions**

507 In this study, the NO removal performance of two activated carbons (OSR700-A900CO₂
 508 and OAK700-A900CO₂) was investigated at low concentrations (2.5–7.5 ppmv) and
 509 temperatures ranging from 25 to 75 °C. The textural properties and surface chemistry of
 510 the activated biochar, which strongly depends on their origin and ash content, are the most

511 influential variables in the NO removal capacity. However, it was found that their impact
512 is greatly conditioned by the temperature.

513 Thus, OSR700-A900CO₂ does not achieve a total NO elimination (62.7 %) at room
514 temperature, but it improves the NO removal capacity with the temperature until it
515 reaches a full NO removal at 50 and 75 °C. These results denote that, at those
516 temperatures, surface oxygenated functional groups, whose population is significantly
517 higher in this sample, may favor the NO oxidation process. The role of the surface
518 oxygenated groups is confirmed by the experiment performed in absence of oxygen, in
519 which the NO removal performance of OSR700-A900CO₂ is better than that exhibited by
520 the OAK activated biochar, although in both cases lower than those obtained in an
521 oxidizing atmosphere. On the other hand, the presence of moisture in the air flow
522 significantly decreased the NO removal performance of OSR700-derived sample due to
523 the competition of water molecules with NO and O₂ by carbon surface functional groups.
524 For the former sample, the generation of a meaningful proportion of oxygenated groups
525 could be aided by its high ash content, very rich in K. In contrast, OAK550-A900CO₂ is
526 the best carbon at room temperature, achieving a full NO elimination efficiency during
527 the 400 min of the assay, even under humid air conditions. This result is attributed to its
528 narrower microporosity centred at around 6 Å, which provides very close contact between
529 NO and O₂, favoring the oxidation process in the carbon active sites. These promising
530 results demonstrate the potential of activated biochars as low-cost and renewable carbons
531 for the removal of NO at low concentrations and temperatures around the ambient, typical
532 conditions of semi-closed environments of urban areas, such as parking lots and tunnels.

533 **CRedit author contribution statement**

534 **Carlos G. Díaz-Maroto:** Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation,
535 Writing – original draft, Visualization; **Ondřej Mašek:** biochar sample, review and
536 editing; **Patricia Pizarro:** Writing – review and editing, Supervision; **David P. Serrano:**
537 Writing – review and editing, Supervision; **Inés Moreno:** Conceptualization, Validation,
538 Writing – review and editing, Supervision; **Javier Feroso:** Conceptualization,
539 Methodology, Validation, Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Supervision,
540 Funding acquisition.

541

542 **Declaration of competing interest**

543 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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